

Computational and Experimental studies and biological activity prediction on Octrizole- an insight into antidiabetic activity.

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Abstract

Octrizole, a heterocyclic aromatic compound was computationally investigated in this work and computational techniques were chosen considering their efficiency and low cost. Density Functional Theory approach with the basis set B3LYP was employed. A minimum energy structure is obtained. Structure interpretation of the chosen compound was carried out using molecular geometry, Vibrational analysis (theoretical and experimental) and NMR analysis. Stability and reactivity prediction of Octrizole were done using UV analysis and FMO studies. Global parameters provided insights into the electronic properties as well. MEP map presents the reactive sites and possible interactions. NLO properties of the chosen compound were calculated. Topological studies (ELF and LOL) are also done. Molecular interactions were identified in the RDG plot and atomic charges present in the title compound were studied. Pharmacological studies were carried out to study the drug-like properties which are also compared with the standard drug Metformin. Ramachandran plot of proteins identified the protein stability. Molecular docking studies on Octrizole were employed to study the protein ligand interactions and the title compound exhibits a better interaction than the standard drug. Theoretical findings predict that Octrizole might be a potential compound to treat Diabetics.

Keywords: DFT, Benzotriazole Moiety, Heterocyclic, Molecular Docking, Anti-Diabetic;

1 Introduction

Benzotriazole derivatives have versatile biological properties and are under wide investigation, where benzotriazole is a bicyclic, heterocyclic compound with two benzene rings and three nitrogen atoms, demonstrates a range of biological and pharmacological characteristics [1, 2]. Benzotriazole derivatives possess antibacterial [3], antiprotozoal [4], antiviral [5] and antiproliferative [6] activity. Most potent antibacterial drugs are heterocyclic molecules with nitrogen atoms. 3-(benzotriazol-1-yl)-1-(4-bromophenyl)-2-(1,2,4-triazol-1-yl)propan-1-one shows great antibacterial activity [7]. Hepatitis C virus and West Nile virus are inhibited by tetra bromo benzotriazole and its derivatives [8]. The cellular proliferation of several liquid and solid human cancers was inhibited by compounds 3-Aryl-2-(1H-Benzotriazol-1-yl) Acrylo Nitriles [9]. Significant anti-inflammatory and antinociceptive effects were exhibited by 2-(Benzotriazol-1/2-yl) Propionicacids [10]. In the process of finding and developing new drugs, Benzotriazole nucleus seems to be a particularly intriguing scaffold.

Diabetes is the elevated blood glucose level and is a metabolic condition. The search for finding an ideal anti diabetic drug lowering blood glucose level continues and its development is still challenging. DFT studies are performed in determining the quantum chemical descriptors help in drug development. Pharmacokinetic properties namely, absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion (ADME) are essential during drug design in finding potential compounds for diabetes. α -Amylase, an enzyme crucial for breaking down dietary starch into glucose where large starch molecules cannot cross the blood-brain barrier to supply glucose to the brain. To address this, α -amylase breaks down these large molecules into smaller sugar fragments that can pass through the barrier. Excessive breakdown of starch into sugars leads to elevated blood glucose. In response, insulin triggers cells to absorb and metabolize this surplus sugar, storing it as glycogen for later energy use. In a healthy individual, this cycle of starch breakdown and glucose regulation occurs continuously. However, in certain situations, excessive amylase activity coupled with insufficient insulin or insulin resistance causes blood glucose levels to rise [11]. α -Amylase is crucially targeted in the development of drugs to combat diabetes and molecular docking studies analyses the interaction of α -Amylase with ligands [12]. Metformin is a standard drug in treating diabetes and the newly developing drug candidates are comparing with it to study the potential of developing drugs [13].

Potential of benzotriazole derivatives results in choosing the title compound Octrizole which has an antidiabetic property. The IUPAC name of chosen compound is 2-(2-Hydroxy-5-tert-

octylphenyl) benzotriazole with molecular formula $C_{20}H_{25}N_3O$, and it contains 49 atoms in total. Chosen compound has a molecular weight of 323.43g/mol. Extensive literature survey reveals, that no studies using Density Functional Theory or molecular docking have been carried out as of yet on this compound. In understanding the scope and application of this derivative, an attempt is made to analyze this compound completely. Structural analysis of Octrizole was employed using DFT studies. Biological evaluation was employed to study biological activities and pharmaceutical applications of the title compound.

2 Experimental details

2-(2-Hydroxy-5-tert-octylphenyl) Benzotriazole (98% purity), is sourced from TCI Chemicals, India. FT IR, FT Raman, were employed at SAIF, IITM, India. KBr sampling technique is used for obtaining FT IR spectrum within a range from 4000 to 400cm^{-1} and FT Raman spectrum is from 4000 to 100cm^{-1} . Evaluation of Octrizole for *in vitro* cytotoxicity activity on Rat Skeletal Muscle (L6) cell line was held at Radiant Research Services Private limited, Bangaluru, India.

3 Computational details

Gaussian16W [14], and Gaussview [15] software serve as the tools for DFT calculations. Gaussview is used in visualizing optimized structure. Basis set for Gaussian calculations is 6-311G++(d,p), and the functional is B3LYP. Vibrational assignments can be acquired using VEDA software [16]. Employing Multiwfn 3.8 [17], wave-functional analysis (ELF, LOL, RDG, and charge transfer) has been performed. Drug-likeness characteristics are assessed using the online SwissADME program [18]. To determine the bioactivity of Octrizole, the PASS online tool [19] is utilized. Molecular docking uses the AutoDock Tools 1.5.6 software [20] and Discovery Studio [21] is utilized for visualization.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Molecular structure

Molecular geometry is the three-dimensional, spatial arrangement of atoms in a molecule. Optimized structure (highly stable and low-energy) for Octrizole was obtained and is given in Fig.1. Bond parameters are presented in Table 1. Longest bonds are seen between carbon atoms due to their repulsive forces. C5–C7 has a maximum bond length of 1.572Å . Shortest Bond length (0.972Å) was found between O1 and H45 which may be due to the higher electronegativity value of oxygen than hydrogen and it might be a suitable site for protein interaction for biological application. Largest bond angle identified is 129.7° and between N3-

C19-C21 and N4-C20-C22. Least bond angle (102.5°) was identified between N2-N4-C20 atoms and N2-N3-C19 atoms. In the triazole ring, nitrogen atoms (N2-N3, N2-N4) are 1.340 \AA apart. Two rings are attached to the triazole group. In ring 1, bond length of C8-C15, C8-C14 is 1.370 \AA and C14-C16, C16-C18, C17-C18, C15-C17 is 1.395 \AA . The bond length of C19-C20, C20-C22, C22-C24, C21-C23, C19-C21 is 1.407 \AA and C23-C24 is 1.421 \AA in ring 2. C-H bonds in rings are found to be 1.08 \AA apart. Carbon-carbon and carbon-hydrogen bond lengths and bond angles in the rings are responsible for their symmetrical structure [22,23]. The spectrum of values for bond length and bond angle (Table 1) may suggest that the chosen compound might be biologically active.

Fig. 1. Optimized structure of Octrizole.

Table 1. Optimized molecular geometry of Octrizole.

Parameter Bond length (\AA)	Theoretical data
O1 -C18	1.363
O1-H45	0.972
N2-N3	1.340
N2-N4	1.340

	N2-C16	1.385	
	N3-C19	1.343	
	N4-C20	1.343	
	C5-C7	1.572	
	C5-C8	1.542	
	C5-C9	1.556	
	C5-C10	1.543	
	C6-C7	1.564	
	C6-C11	1.549	
	C6-C12	1.541	
	C6-C13	1.533	
	C7-H25	1.101	
	C7-H26	1.100	
	C8-C14	1.370	
	C8-C15	1.370	
	C9-H27	1.095	
	C9-H28	1.097	
	C9-H29	1.097	
	C10-H30	1.098	
	C10-H31	1.097	
	C10-H32	1.090	
	C11-H33	1.096	
	C11-H34	1.096	
	C11-H35	1.096	
	C12-H36	1.095	
	C12-H37	1.097	
	C12-H38	1.093	
	C13-H39	1.098	
	C13-H40	1.094	
	C13-H41	1.091	
	C14-C16	1.395	
	C14-H42	1.084	
	C15-C17	1.395	
	C15-H43	1.082	
	C16-C18	1.395	
	C17-C18	1.395	
	C17-H44	1.087	
	C19-C20	1.407	
	C19-C21	1.407	
	C20-C22	1.407	
	C21-C23	1.407	
	C21-H46	1.083	
	C22-C24	1.407	
	C22-H47	1.083	
	C23-C24	1.421	
	C23-H48	1.089	
3.2 Vibrational analysis			
Vibrational spectroscopy groups of the title Hydroxy-5-tert-benzotriazole has 49			determines the functional compound. 2-(2-octylphenyl) atoms and 141 vibrational

modes [24]. Theoretical peaks obtained for FTIR in Fig 2(a) and Fig 2(b) assignments are listed in 0.961 since the the gaseous state. O-H between 3600- 3400 cm^{-1} observed O-H peak is at experimentally observed 1 , which are within the found for OH stretching stretching. C-H stretching 3100 cm^{-1} [26]. For the vibration was found CH stretching was cm^{-1} indicating the pure vibrations are seen [27] and the peak was which is found within the IR and FT Raman peaks seen at 1592 cm^{-1} and Standard aromatic N-C 1335 and 1250 cm^{-1} [28] compound, vibrations 1311, 1274 cm^{-1} which N stretching is seen [29] and the observed 1) for chosen compound Theoretical and comparable and determined the functional chosen compound and structure [30,31].

C24-H49	1.089
Bond angle ($^\circ$)	
C18-O1-H45	109.1
O1-C18-C16	121.1
O1-C18-C17	118.9
N3-N2-N4	118.8
N3-N2-C16	120.6
N2-N3-C19	102.5
N4-N2-C16	120.6
N2-N4-C20	102.5
N2-C16-C14	119.3
N2-C16-C18	120.7
N3-C19-C20	108.1
N3-C19-C21	129.7
N4-C20-C19	108.1
N4-C20-C22	129.7
C7-C5-C8	113.0
C7-C5-C9	106.9
C7-C5-C10	110.5
C5-C7-C6	122.5
C5-C7-H25	107.3
C5-C7-H26	107.6
C8-C5-C9	106.5
C8-C5-C10	113.8
C5-C8-C14	118.2
C5-C8-C15	118.1
C9-C5-C10	105.6
C5-C9-H27	113.0
C5-C9-H28	111.3
C5-C9-H29	110.8
C5-C10-H30	111.5
C5-C10-H31	110.7
C5-C10-H32	113.8
C7-C6-C11	107.1
C7-C6-C12	111.9
C7-C6-C13	114.0
C6-C7-H25	107.5
C6-C7-H26	106.3
C11-C6-C12	106.7
C11-C6-C13	107.6
C6-C11-H33	111.1
C6-C11-H34	111.2
C6-C11-H35	111.5
C12-C6-C13	109.2
C6-C12-H36	111.5
C6-C12-H37	111.0

peaks and experimental and FTR and are presented respectively. Vibrational Table 2 with scaling factor calculations were done in stretching is observed [25] and theoretically 3684 cm^{-1} and FT IR peak is at 3641 cm^{-1} range. 100% %PED value indicating the pure is in the range of 3000– title compound, C-H within the range and 100% observed at a peak of 3056 CH stretching. CC bond between 1650 and 1400 observed at 1595 cm^{-1} range. Experimental FT for C-C vibrations were 1597 cm^{-1} respectively. vibrations are between and for the title were observed at 1318, were within the ranges. N- between 1200-1000 cm^{-1} peaks (1190 and 1048 cm^{-1} are in desirable range. Experimental results were vibrational analysis groups present in the thus confirmed the

C6-C12-H38	111.8
C6-C13-H39	110.4
C6-C13-H40	111.6
C6-C13-H41	112.6
H25-C7-H26	104.2
C14-C8-C15	123.7
C8-C14-C16	118.2
C8-C14-H42	120.7
C8-C15-C17	118.2
C8-C15-H43	125.0
H27-C9-H28	107.4
H27-C9-H29	106.6
H28-C9-H29	107.4
H30-C10-H31	106.5
H30-C10-H32	107.2
H31-C10-H32	106.8
H33-C11-H34	107.8
H33-C11-H35	107.5
H34-C11-H35	107.6
H36-C12-H37	107.4
H36-C12-H38	108.8
H37-C12-H38	106.6
H39-C13-H40	106.5
H39-C13-H41	105.5
H40-C13-H41	109.9
C16-C14-H42	121.2
C14-C16-C18	120.0
C17-C15-H43	116.8
C15-C17-C18	120.0
C15-C17-H44	119.2
C16-C18-C17	120.0
C18-C17-H44	120.8
C20-C19-C21	122.2
C19-C20-C22	122.2
C19-C21-C23	114.4
C19-C21-H46	123.4
C20-C22-C24	114.4
C20-C22-H47	123.4
C23-C21-H46	122.2
C21-C23-C24	123.4
C21-C23-H48	118.4
C24-C22-H47	122.3
C22-C24-C23	123.4
C22-C24-H49	118.4
C24-C23-H48	118.2
C23-C24-H49	118.2

Fig. 2(a). FT IR spectra

Fig.2(b) FT Raman spectra

Table 2. Experimental and calculated vibrational spectroscopic data with vibrational assignments on Octrizole.

Modes	Experimental wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)		Theoretical wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)		IR		Raman		Assignments (PED)%
	FT IR	FT Raman	Unscaled	Scaled	Rel	Abs	Rel	Abs	
	141	3641		3834	3684	83	68	160	
140			3207	3082	5	4	106	21	Y CH (93)
139			3204	3079	1	1	22	4	Y CH (91)
138			3200	3075	14	11	313	62	Y CH (91)
137		3071	3196	3072	11	9	51	10	Y CH(90)
136			3180	3056	9	7	192	38	Y CH (100)
135			3167	3044	3	3	59	12	Y CH(92)
134	3146		3152	3029	16	13	142	28	Y CH(97)
133			3120	2998	31	25	42	8	Y CH (87)
132			3106	2985	27	22	48	10	Y CH(94)
131			3104	2983	19	15	29	6	Y CH(97)
130			3097	2976	26	21	53	10	Y CH(96)
129			3090	2969	93	76	157	31	Y CH(52)
128			3085	2965	86	71	134	27	Y CH(85)
127			3085	2965	3	2	16	3	Y CH(83)
126			3080	2960	8	6	27	5	Y CH(94)
125			3078	2958	44	36	82	16	Y CH(84)
124	2942	2954	3072	2952	5	4	17	3	Y CH(98)
123			3045	2927	19	15	29	6	Y CH(96)
122			3032	2914	31	25	504	100	Y CH(78)
121			3027	2909	27	22	268	53	Y CH(73)
120			3022	2904	34	28	74	15	Y CH(86)
119		2903	3020	2903	35	29	9	2	Y CH(82)

118	2895		3013	2896	30	24	43	8	Y CH(76)
117			3005	2888	15	12	16	3	Y CH(82)
116	1787	1597	1660	1595	3	3	9	2	Y CC(50)
115	1592		1652	1588	15	12	59	12	Y CC(31)
114			1634	1570	4	3	422	84	Y CC(44)+ βCCC(21)
113			1593	1531	13	11	153	30	βCCC(20)+ βCNN (42)
112	1510	1516	1547	1487	122	100	70	14	βHCC (49)+ βCCC(10) Y CC(23) +
111			1535	1475	1	1	10	2	Y NC(29)+ βHCC(35)
110			1530	1470	15	12	3	1	βHCH(62)
109			1522	1463	12	10	4	1	βHCH(40)
108	1455		1512	1453	10	8	7	1	βHCH(43)
107			1509	1450	7	6	3	1	βHCH(43)
106			1506	1448	15	12	2	0	βHCH(40)
105			1498	1440	2	2	19	4	βHCH(41)
104			1494	1436	4	3	50	10	βHCH(46)
103			1489	1431	2	1	24	5	βHCH(66)
102			1487	1429	2	1	155	31	Y CC(26)
101			1486	1428	4	3	184	37	βHCH(38)
100			1484	1426	1	0	4	1	βHCH(47)
99		1420	1479	1421	1	1	1	0	βHCH(34)
98			1456	1399	16	13	48	10	Y CC(14)+ βHCC(10)
97	1386		1436	1380	10	8	0	0	βHCH(40)
96			1431	1376	7	6	206	41	
95			1425	1369	7	6	21	4	βHCH(56)
94		1350	1405	1350	6	5	1	0	βHCH(80)
93			1401	1346	15	12	0	0	βHCH(62)

92			1397	1343	3	2	0	0	β HCH(43)
91			1382	1328	3	2	2	0	β HCC(10) + τ HCCC(48)
90			1371	1318	8	6	2	0	γ NC(16)+ β HCC(27)
89			1364	1311	45	37	4	1	γ CC(14)+ γ NC(30)
88			1362	1309	34	28	5	1	β HOC(15)+ β HCC(22)
87	1300	1302	1350	1297	64	52	12	2	β HOC(11)+ β HCC(38)
86			1325	1274	61	50	190	38	γ NC(26)+ β HCC(10)
85			1318	1267	2	2	117	23	β HCC(10)
84	1243		1298	1248	37	30	10	2	γ OC(37)
83			1284	1234	14	12	7	1	β HCC(25)
82			1267	1218	24	20	5	1	γ OC(10)+ τ HCCC(10)
81	1207		1263	1214	22	18	7	1	γ CC(10)+ τ HCCC(13)
80			1239	1190	23	19	0	0	γ NN(71)
79			1232	1184	3	2	8	2	γ CC(11)+ τ HCCC(26)
78			1211	1164	5	4	6	1	γ CC(11)+ τ HCCC(21)
77			1201	1154	13	10	5	1	β HOC(21)+ β HCC(44)
76	1133		1186	1140	5	4	12	2	β HCC(10)
75			1169	1124	17	14	1	0	β HCC(59)
74			1167	1122	69	57	8	2	β HOC(21)
73			1151	1106	3	2	10	2	γ CC(30)+ β HCC(62)
72			1139	1094	3	3	9	2	γ CC(29)+

								τ HCCC(13)
71	1068		1123	1080	20	16	7	1
70			1091	1048	24	20	18	4
								γ NN(19)+ β CCC(22)
69			1059	1018	0	0	1	0
								τ HCCC(23)
68			1048	1007	0	0	2	0
								τ HCCC(26)
67		994	1027	987	0	0	0	0
								τ HCCC(36)
66	971		1014	975	1	1	139	27
								β CCN(46)+ β NNN(14)
65			990	952	0	0	1	0
								τ HCCC(75)
64			989	950	10	9	14	3
								β CCN(24)+ β NNN(10)
63			984	946	15	12	27	5
								γ CC(22)
62			963	925	0	0	1	0
								τ HCCC(97)
61			961	924	0	0	0	0
								τ HCCC(38)
60	918		959	922	1	1	0	0
								τ HCCC(49)+ τ CCCC(13)
59			948	911	5	4	4	1
								β HCC(11)+ τ HCCC(13)
58			942	905	1	1	0	0
								τ HCCN(10)
57			936	899	2	2	3	1
								γ CC(11)+ β HCC(15)+ β CCC(15)+ τ HCCN(11)
56			931	895	2	1	4	1
								γ CC(12)+ β CCC(36)
55		884	921	885	2	1	9	2
								γ CC(20)+ τ HCCN(13)
54	878		913	877	7	6	35	7
								τ HCCN(34)
53			887	853	11	9	68	13
								γ CC(10)+ β CCC(10)
52			872	838	3	2	5	1
								γ CC(26)+ τ HCCC(12)
51			858	824	0	0	0	0
								τ HCCN(84)
50	801		829	797	10	8	15	3
								γ CC(30)

49		822	790	29	24	1	0	τ HCCC(67)+ ω OCCC(15)
48		816	784	17	14	7	1	Υ CC(24)+ β CCC(12)
47	743	777	746	1	0	0	0	τ HCCC(20)+ τ CCCC(34)+ τ CNNC(27)
46		760	730	72	59	0	0	τ HCCC(84)
45		752	723	2	2	10	2	τ HCCC(14)+ ω OCCC(13)+ ω NCCC(16)
44		750	721	4	4	9	2	Υ CC(34)
43		732	704	7	6	2	0	
42	687	699	671	6	5	2	0	ω NCNN(48)
41	648	672	646	1	1	4	1	Υ CC(21)+ β CCC(13)
40		662	636	12	10	5	1	Υ NN(14)+ ω NCNN(10)
39		634	609	0	0	11	2	Υ CC(45)+ β CNN(28)
38		585	562	3	3	1	0	β CCC(13)+ β CCN(13)
37		583	560	2	2	1	0	τ HCCC(21)+ τ CCCC(24)+ τ CCNC(36)
36		560	538	2	2	3	1	β CCN(10)+ β CCC(11)
35		552	531	3	3	3	1	
34		514	494	3	3	12	2	
33		504	484	4	3	2	0	β OCC(15)
32		473	454	1	1	3	1	ω CCCC(17)
31		448	431	7	6	1	0	
30		443	426	4	4	1	0	τ CCCC(33)
29		431	414	2	2	6	1	τ CCCC(22)+ τ OCCC(12)

28		422	406	0	0	0	0	τ CCCC(39)
27		395	380	1	1	1	0	β CCCC(37)
26		380	366	0	0	0	0	β CCCC(49)+ ω CCCC(12)
25		365	351	1	1	1	0	β CCCC(11)
24		359	345	2	2	0	0	β CCCC(13)+ τ HCCC(44)
23		346	333	2	2	1	0	ω CCCC(11)
22		310	298	11	9	3	1	
21		306	294	58	47	2	0	β CCCC(35)
20		297	285	8	7	0	0	τ HOCC(61)
19		291	280	6	5	1	0	τ HCCC(30)+ ω CCCC(10)
18		283	272	4	3	3	1	β CCCC(27)
17		278	267	2	2	2	0	
16		271	260	1	1	0	0	τ CCCC(22)+ τ CNNC(24)+ ω CCNC(36)
15		268	257	1	0	7	1	β CCCC(10)+ τ HCCC(11)
14		261	250	0	0	2	0	τ HCCC(51)
13		246	237	0	0	1	0	β CCCC(10)
12		231	222	0	0	1	0	τ HCCC(12)
11		222	213	0	0	1	0	
10		197	189	0	0	2	0	
9		177	171	0	0	1	0	β CCCC(36)
8		153	147	1	1	2	0	β CCCC(24)+ τ CCCC(11)
7		129	124	0	0	1	0	τ CCCC(64)
6	93	88	84	3	2	2	0	β NNC(22)+ τ CCCC(12)+ τ NCCC(23)
5		55	53	0	0	5	1	τ CNNC(17)+

							τ CCCC(13)+ ω CCCC(14) β NNCC(13)+ τ
4	47	45	1	1	5	1	CCCC(11)+ ω CCCC(16)
3	39	37	0	0	0	0	τ NNCC(21)+ τ CCCC(52)
2	26	25	0	0	2	0	τ NNCC(51)+ τ CCCC(25)
1	25	24	0	0	8	2	τ NNCC(12)+ τ CCCC(53)

γ - stretching, β – In plane bending, ω – Out of plane bending, τ – Torsion.

*Scaling factor 0.961 for B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) basis set.

Rel- Relative

Abs- Absolute

Normalised to 100.

3.3 Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) Analysis

NMR spectroscopy is a technique based on shielding effect due to electron density around nucleus, exploits the magnetic characteristics of particular atomic nuclei. Density Functional Theory (DFT), and GIAO method were used to predict and interpret ^{13}C NMR and ^1H NMR spectra. Electrons produce a shielding effect on ^{13}C and ^1H nuclei from external magnetic field. Larger electron density around nucleus creates a greater shielding effect which make the atoms to observed at lower chemical shifts and with a low ppm values known as upfield region. Higher ppm values are due to low electron density which refer to a higher chemical shift and deshielding which is termed as downfield region [32-35]. Chemical shifts determine the chemical environment of the molecule and chemical shifts are presented in Table 3 and ^{13}C NMR and ^1H NMR spectra obtained are shown in Fig. 3(a) and Fig. 3(b) respectively. The chemical shift in ^{13}C NMR (fig 3(a)) spectral ranges was between 26.18ppm and 155.11ppm. Maximum ppm value was observed for C18 (155.11ppm) which is bonded with an electronegative oxygen atom (O1) resulting a low electron density hence deshielding effect. Standard chemical shifts for the carbon atoms attached to heteroatoms or alkyl groups were between 138-160ppm and chemical shifts for the carbon atoms (C18, C8, C19, C20) were found to be 155.11ppm, 151.12ppm, 150.80ppm, 150.17ppm respectively which is in the desired range. A chemical shift for C7, C5, C6, C9, C11, C12, C13, and C10 was found between 26 and

60 ppm indicating that these are alkyl carbon atoms and a lower chemical shift indicating the higher electron density around nucleus and thus a greater shielding effect. A chemical shift for C16 was found to be 135.45ppm interprets that C16 belongs to arenes or methyl-substituted arenes. Normal chemical shift ranges for internal aromatic carbon atoms namely (C14, C15, C23, C24) are between 129.5-133ppm indicating higher ppm value due to lower electron density. These results were complimented by the molecular geometry for internal aromatic carbon atoms which has similar bond lengths. C17, C21, and C22 have a chemical shift of 117.74, 123.4, and 124.3 ppm respectively, where the standard range for protonated arenes is from 118-129.5 ppm [36].

¹H NMR spectra ranged from 0.418 ppm to 8.149 ppm. Hydrogen atoms (H 47, H46, H42, H49, H48, H43, H44) are attached to aromatic rings showing higher chemical shifts between 6-8.5 ppm. Higher chemical shifts for hydrogen atoms in aromatic rings indicating the low electron density and a deshielding effect suggesting the electron withdrawing nature of aromatic rings. H45 attached to the electronegative oxygen atom has a chemical shift of 3.82, where the normative range is between 3-4 ppm and deshielding effect observed for H45 atom was due to low electron density associated with H45 which might be suitable for biological activity. Hydrogen atoms (H32, H25, H38, H30, H27, H29, H31, H33, H34, H36, H37, H28, H35, H39, H41 and H40) present in alkyl groups shows chemical shifts of 1ppm.

Equivalent chemical shifts obtained for hydrogen atoms (H 47, H46, H42, H49, H48, H43, H44) attached to aromatic rings suggesting that these atoms experience equivalent deshielding effects and thus significant in determining the symmetry of chosen compound. Bond lengths of hydrogen atoms (H 47, H46, H42, H49, H48, H43, H44) attached to aromatic rings has equivalent bond lengths (Table 1) suggesting the symmetrical structure of rings and which is line with the NMR results.

Structure determination, symmetry and electronic interactions of the chosen compound were done by analyzing the chemical shifts obtained and comparing them with the normative chemical shifts of different functional groups [37, 38].

Fig. 3(a) C NMR

Fig. 3 (b) H NMR

Table 3 Calculated chemical shift in NMR

Atoms	Chemical shift
18-C	155.1105
8-C	151.1276
20-C	150.8043
19-C	150.1777
16-C	135.4596
14-C	133.861
15-C	131.4909
23-C	130.6166
24-C	130.1308
22-C	124.318
21-C	123.4456
17-C	117.7417
7-C	59.26357
5-C	44.58504
6-C	38.31644
9-C	37.79009
11-C	35.72784
12-C	32.28433
13-C	26.88927

10-C	26.18888
47-H	8.149078
46-H	8.103699
42-H	7.795965
49-H	7.536175
48-H	7.534858
43-H	7.427326
44-H	6.623649
45-H	3.828516
26-H	2.221889
32-H	1.642708
25-H	1.465021
38-H	1.432951
30-H	1.298181
27-H	1.197861
29-H	1.106231
31-H	1.094765
33-H	1.011165
34-H	0.983253
36-H	0.877118
37-H	0.870438
28-H	0.748518
35-H	0.637807
39-H	0.483564
41-H	0.482071
40-H	0.418597

3.4 UV analysis

UV-Vis spectroscopy is a technique that probes the interaction between matter and electromagnetic radiation in the UV and visible spectral ranges. Electromagnetic spectrum relevant to UV-Vis spectroscopy spans from 200 nm to 800 nm and the portion below 400 nm is designated as the UV region, while wavelengths exceeding 400 nm fall into the visible region. [39, 40]. Fig. 4 displays the theoretical UV-Vis spectrum of the title compound and Table 4 provides the corresponding electronic properties. Maximum absorption wavelength for Octrizole was observed at 270.86 nm, a value that falls in mid-UV region, implies that exciting an electron to a higher orbital necessitates a moderate energy suggesting that the investigated compound have moderate stability and moderate reactivity [41].

Fig. 4 UV spectra

Table 4 UV analysis

Energy (cm ⁻¹)	Wavelength(nm)	Osc.Strength	Assignments >10%
32470.49	307.97	0.1643	HOMO->LUMO (93%)
34401.39	290.68	0.0502	H-1->LUMO (93%)
36926.73	270.806	0.3133	H-2->LUMO (90%)

3.5 Frontier Molecular Orbital (FMO)

Insights into a molecule's bioactivity can be effectively gained through the analysis of its molecular orbitals, and the energy gap between the highest occupied and lowest unoccupied molecular orbitals is a fundamental predictor of its stability and reactivity. A smaller energy gap between the HOMO and LUMO predicts higher reactivity, whereas a larger gap suggests lower reactivity [42-44]. Fig.5 showcases the HOMO-LUMO energy transition and Table 5 shows the global parameters. HOMO energy was found to be -6.359 eV and LUMO was -1.749 eV and the energy gap was 4.610 eV. Calculated wavelength using the expression $E = hv$ was found to be 269 nm and thus, Frontier Molecular Orbital (FMO) studies and UV-Vis

spectroscopy are consistent, both suggesting moderate stability and moderate reactivity for the molecule. An ionization potential (IP) of 6.359 eV was calculated for the compound, representing the energy needed to remove an electron. This IP value is inherently related to the HOMO energy, which corresponds to the orbital from where the electron might be removed. Calculated electron affinity (EA) of 1.749 eV for the compound represents the energy liberated when an electron is added to it. This value is directly associated with the energy of LUMO, which is the orbital that accepts electrons [45]. Title compound displays an electronegativity of 4.054, a measure of its ability to attract the electrons in a shared pair during bond formation. [45]. A Chemical Hardness (CH) value of 2.305 indicating that the chosen compound might be moderately stable suggesting that, it is a moderately hard material and the same was predicted in UV analysis also [46]. A softness value of 0.217 which is less than 2 [47] indicates that the title compound might be less toxic. Electrophilicity index (3.565) reflects a compound's electrophilic nature where the EI value was found to be greater than 1.5 eV indicating the strong electrophilic nature and thus, its potential biological activity [48-50].

Fig. 5. Frontier molecular orbital of Octrizole.

Table 5. calculated global parameters of Octrizole.

Parameter	Value
HOMO (eV)	-6.359
LUMO (eV)	-1.749
Ionization potential	6.359
Electron affinity	1.749
Energy gap (eV)	4.610
Electronegativity	4.054
Chemical potential	-4.054
Chemical hardness	2.305
Chemical softness	0.217

Electrophilicity index 3.565

3.6 MOLECULAR ELECTROSTATIC POTENTIAL

Molecular Electrostatic Potential creates a colored plot of Octrizole in three dimensions. MEP assesses the molecule's low and high electron densities and represents electron-donor and acceptor species. Color grading indicates that electrophilic attacking sites are found in red areas with negative potential in the map, whereas nucleophilic attacking sites are found in blue regions with positive potential and neutral electron density in green areas. Fig. 6 displays MEP map and scale starting from $-6.466e^{-2}$ to $6.466e^{-2}$ [51,52]. Blue region near H45 indicating the positive potential and therefore H45 might be a nucleophilic attacking site, which is bonded with an electronegative oxygen atom (O1), has more affinity towards electrons making electron cloud shift towards O1. Deshielding effect due to low electron density was observed near H45 in NMR spectra supporting the results obtained in MEP. Nitrogen atoms (N2, N3, N4) and oxygen (O1) in the map have negative potential which is seen in red region suggesting electrophilic attacking sites. Low electron density and deshielding effect observed for C18 in ^{13}C NMR, which is bonded with O1 provided a good agreement with the MEP results. Most of the regions in a MEP map are colored green, typically indicating a neutral or near-neutral electrostatic potential and these areas have a balanced distribution of electrons, resulting in neither a significant excess nor deficiency of electrons [53].

Fig. 6. Molecular electrostatic potential Map of Octrizole.

3.7 Electron Localization Function and Localized Orbital Locator

ELF & LOL are two dimensional colored maps used in determining and approximating the electron density of the title compound [54] and are presented in Fig.7(a). and Fig.7(b).

In molecular systems, the electron distribution and Pauli's repulsion between electrons is applied to determine the Electron Localization Function (ELF) [55]. ELF scale extends from 0, represented by blue colour refers least Pauli's repulsion, to 1 represented by red colour indicates the strongest Pauli repulsion. ELF map of Octrizole displays hydrogen atoms (H34, H36) in the red area indicating strong Paul's repulsion and maximum probability of finding an electron exists. Nitrogen atom (N4) and carbon atoms (C8, C14, C20, C23, C24) are in the blue area suggesting the least Paul's repulsion.

LOL maps visualize the degree of electron depletion through color gradients [56]. LOL scale extends from 0, represented by blue colour indicating minimum electron depletion region, to 0.8, shown in red colour refers to maximum level of electron depletion. Hydrogen atoms (H34, H36) are in the red area, and Nitrogen atom (N4) and carbon atoms (C8, C14, C20, C23, C24) are in the blue area predicting the minimum and maximum depletion respectively. LOL offers a perspective that complements the ELF map and determined the electron distribution, Pauli' repulsion and electron depletion within the chosen compound which provides insight into the possible interactions for Octrizole. Low ppm value was found for H34, H36 indicating the larger electron density and greater shielding effect. ELF and LOL map of Octrizole displays hydrogen atoms (H34, H36) has strong Paul's repulsion and maximum probability of finding an electron near it and is in line with NMR results [57].

Fig. 7(a). ELF coloured map of Octrizole.

Fig. 7(b). LOL map of Octrizole.

3.8 Reduced Density Gradient (RDG) Analysis

RDG is employed to calculate non-covalent interactions with Hessian matrix and electron density [58]. Colored RDG maps can be obtained using Mutiwavewfn 3.8 and VMD software and Fig.8. shows the RDG map created for Octrizole where $\text{sign}(\lambda_2)\rho$ is the electron density Hessian matrix. $\text{Sign}(\lambda_2)\rho$ greater than 0 and red isosurfaces indicate repulsive interactions or steric clashes, $\text{sign}(\lambda_2)\rho$ less than 0 and blue isosurfaces indicate attractive interactions and $\text{sign}(\lambda_2)\rho$ near 0 and green isosurfaces are indicator of weak interactions like Van der Waal interactions. In fig. 8, sharp peaks were seen in the red region and red isosurfaces are observed near aromatic rings in Octrizole suggesting the strong repulsive interactions present in aromatic rings and the repulsion or steric clashes might be due to the closely occupied electron clouds. On comparing results from the molecular geometry of chosen compound, the longest bond lengths were observed between the carbon atoms in aromatic rings and the results obtained in RDG are in line with each other. Green isosurface near oxygen atom indicating weak van der Waals forces near it and it might be due to the partial negative charge on oxygen atom [59,60]. RDG plot provided information on the interactions within the molecule which helps in understanding the biological activity of the chosen molecule.

Fig. 8. RDG coloured map of Octrizole.

3.9 Mulliken Population Analysis (MPA) and Natural Population Analysis (NPA)

DFT-based Mulliken Population Analysis (MPA) is a computational approach for estimating atomic charges in a molecule and was determined by calculating the electron population associated with each atom. Atomic charges are a crucial factor in understanding molecular systems. Natural Population Analysis (NPA) gives a more accurate account of electronic charge

spread throughout a molecular system, and its calculations are numerically stable. MPA and NPA was obtained using the DFT technique is presented in Table 6. Positive charges were observed for all the hydrogen atoms present in the chosen compound and a maximum positive charge was observed for the H45 atom in NPA (0.470). In molecular geometry, the H45 was bonded with an electronegative oxygen atom giving rise to a partial positive charge on H45 atom. Positive potential near H45 was observed in MEP map indicating the electron-deficient region and the maximum positive charge observed in NPA also predicts the same. NPA analysis reveal the presence of positive charge on carbon atoms (C16, C18, C19, C20) that are attached to electronegative Oxygen (O1) and nitrogen atoms (N2, N3, N4) which might be due to the electronegativity differences between these bonding atoms. Other carbon atoms attached to hydrogen atoms showed negative where hydrogen atoms have a lower electronegativity than carbon. Oxygen atom (O1) and nitrogen atoms (N3, N4) have a negative charge, and N2 has a very low positive charge observed in NPA might be due to the higher electronegativities of O1, N2, N3 and N4. On analysing MEP map, similar trends were observed for these atoms indicating electron-rich regions. Charges obtained for atoms in NPA were in good agreement with the results obtained in MEP analysis and which determine the possible interactions of the chosen compound [61,62].

Table 6 Mulliken and natural population of Octrizole.

Atoms	Mulliken population	Natural population
O1	-0.18938	-0.65284
N2	0.448659	0.01194
N3	-0.02334	-0.26724
N4	0.096663	-0.23877
C5	0.184084	-0.09174
C6	0.216915	-0.09289
C7	-0.34138	-0.36229
C8	0.783221	-0.03514
C9	-0.55014	-0.55594
C10	-0.35781	-0.568
C11	-0.54178	-0.56411
C12	-0.58161	-0.56814
C13	-0.5209	-0.57395
C14	-0.58924	-0.16721
C15	-0.41173	-0.18319
C16	-0.35791	0.10385
C17	-0.30581	-0.26328
C18	-0.07385	0.32369
C19	0.585641	0.09398

C20	-0.04804	0.09176
C21	-0.46211	-0.19781
C22	-0.66586	-0.194
C23	-0.17662	-0.20255
C24	-0.25133	-0.20502
H25	0.189825	0.19881
H26	0.170363	0.19943
H27	0.134197	0.20098
H28	0.166805	0.20509
H29	0.148034	0.19864
H30	0.143793	0.2011
H31	0.184611	0.20697
H32	0.118729	0.19835
H33	0.135708	0.20078
H34	0.135734	0.19718
H35	0.152314	0.19938
H36	0.145523	0.19617
H37	0.149969	0.19872
H38	0.126876	0.19742
H39	0.168311	0.19822
H40	0.212077	0.20876
H41	0.14036	0.19978
H42	0.236298	0.22519
H43	0.169733	0.21188
H44	0.159848	0.2024
H45	0.268852	0.47043
H46	0.162239	0.21597
H47	0.17584	0.21703
H48	0.17089	0.20508
H49	0.166724	0.20523

3.10 Non-Linear optical activity

Non-linear optical activity arises from attractive forces of the electromagnetic fields and Table 7 presents the NLO parameters determined by quantum chemical calculations using DFT methods. Non-linear optical (NLO) characteristic of organic molecules was elucidated by the hyperpolarizability component. Compounds that exhibit greater hyper-polarizabilities than urea fall under nonlinear optical (NLO) materials categories. Calculations are made in x, y, and z coordinates for Dipole moment, Polarizability, First order Hyper polarizability. Octrizole has a dipole moment (m) of 0.773D. Polarizability (α) and hyper polarizability (β) was found to be $4.2299E^{-23}$ and $9.1484E^{-30}$ respectively, which is more than prototype reference molecule urea ($0.452E^{-23}$ and $0.333E^{-30}$). A high polarizability and hyperpolarizability value indicate that the electron cloud can be easily distorted which results in stronger dipoles might contribute to

Van der Waals forces (London forces) which is an interaction originated due to the dipoles. Van der Waals forces near oxygen atom were determined in RDG studies as well [63,64]. Van der Waals forces facilitate the interaction between title compound and biological systems, potentially leading to increased biological activity.

Table 7 Predicted dipole moment, polarizability and first hyper polarizability for basis Octrizole.

Parameters	Value
β_{xxx}	679.6316276
β_{xxy}	462.0800276
β_{xyy}	153.9374514
β_{yyy}	145.2489506
β_{zxx}	128.3619
β_{xyz}	10.6386628
β_{zyy}	39.8919506
β_{xzz}	-42.1649442
β_{yzz}	69.2864657
β_{zzz}	24.646738
β_{tot} (a.u)	1058.933
β_{tot} (e.s.u)	9.1484E-30
α_{xx}	395.725147
α_{xy}	32.8652095
α_{yy}	263.736642
α_{xz}	-14.0009817
α_{yz}	24.5444005
α_{zz}	196.78926
α (a.u)	285.4170
α (e.s.u)	4.2299E-23
$\Delta \alpha$ (a.u)	707.4845
$\Delta \alpha$ (e.s.u)	1.0485E-23
μ_x	-0.6055856
μ_y	-0.4671337
μ_z	-0.1162129
μ (D)	0.77359

3.11 Pharmacological studies

Drug likeness parameters were employed using SwissADME online software where Lipinski's rule of Five is a guide in choosing a strong drug candidate. Table 8 presented the calculated

drug likeness parameters of Ocotrizole and a standard drug. Hydrogen Bond Donor count was found to be 1 and Hydrogen Bond Acceptor count was 3. There are 4 rotatable bonds in the title compound and the molecular weight was found to be 323.43g/mol. There are no infractions found for the title compound and the parameters are within the preferred range [65,66]. High gastrointestinal absorption indicates that the title compound is efficiently taken up from the digestive system. The blood-brain barrier (BBB) strictly regulates the passage of substances from the bloodstream into the brain. Consequently, the absence of BBB permeation indicates that the title compound is unlikely to enter the brain tissue [67]. A positive lipophilicity value of 3.46 indicates that the chosen compound might be more easily dissolvable into the lipid-based membranes than the standard drug whose lipophilicity value was found to be -0.56 suggesting its inability to dissolve into the lipid-based membranes. Bioavailability score of 0.55 indicates good absorption and distribution into the body like Metformin [68,69]. Drug likeness parameters obtained fall within the normative ranges and is comparable with the standard drug, Metformin, indicating the favourable drug character of 2-(2-Hydroxy-5-tert-octylphenyl) benzotriazole.

Table 8 Drug-likeness parameters for Ocotrizole.

Descriptor	Desirable range	Value for the title compound	Value for std drug(metformin)
Hydrogen Bond donors	<5	1	3
Hydrogen Bond acceptors	<10	3	2
M log P	<4.15	3.46	-0.56
GI absorption	-	high	high
Lipinski violation	-	0 violation	0 violation
skin permeation	-	-3.05cm/s	-7.99
molar refractivity	40-130	99.13	36.93
Bioavailability score	-	0.55	0.55
Number of rotatable bonds	<10	4	2
Molecular weight	<500	323.43 g/mol	129.16g/mol

8 In vitro cytotoxicity activity

In *in vitro* cytotoxicity investigation, Rat Skeletal Muscle (L6) cells were exposed to varying concentrations of 2-(2-Hydroxy-5-tert-octylphenyl) benzotriazole, ranging from 1000 to 7.8µg/mL given in Table 9. MTT assay was used to measure metabolic activity using a colorimetric determination to examine the cytotoxic effect of specific concentrations. Number of viable cells are examined in MTT assay. Rat Skeletal Muscle (L6) cell line cytotoxicity,

measured in terms of percentage cell viability, was found to be $85.39 \pm 3.02\%$ at $1000\mu\text{g/mL}$ concentration in the current investigation. An increased cell viability along with the decreased concentration is found.

Table 9. Analysis of the in vitro cytotoxicity of Octrizole against Rat Skeletal Muscle (L6) cell line by MTT assay.

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Percentage cells viable after treatment
1000	85.39 ± 3.02
500	90.05 ± 2.39
250	93.85 ± 2.57
125	94.58 ± 1.85
62.5	95.02 ± 2.17
31.25	96.96 ± 0.54
15.628	98.85 ± 1.20
7.8	99.14 ± 1.00

3.12 Ramachandran plot

Representation of Ramachandran plots served as verification of the protein stability and binding affinity. 4GQR (Human Pancreatic alpha-amylase in complex with myricetin) [70], 7KPI (Crystal structure of the SPOP MATH domain) [71], and 4W93 (Human pancreatic alpha-amylase in complex with montbretin A) are proteins with properties against diabetics were chosen for docking. Using Discovery Studio software RC plots were obtained and shown in Fig. 9(a), 9(b), and 9(c). Allowed domain contains a majority of the protein's sequences and a few amino acids are located in the restricted region. Stability of 4GQR and 7KPI, 4W93 was indicated by their RC plots, as a large number of amino acid residues are located inside the permitted zone and these proteins are suitable in molecular docking [72].

9(a) 4GQR

9(b)7KPI

9(c) 4W93

Fig. 9. Ramachandran plots of proteins

3.13 Molecular docking studies

Docking is a widely used method for researching drugs and is an expressive technique and efficient method to explain ligand-protein interaction. Biological activity of Octrizole was assessed with PASS online program and potency of compound under study to treat diabetics was determined. Chosen compound was docked against 4GQR and 7KPI, 4W93 proteins using AutoDock tools 1.5.6, and visualization was done with Discovery Studio visualizer. Docking results are listed in Table 10 and ligand-protein interaction in 2 dimensions and 3 dimensions are given in Fig.10. Binding energy for 4GQR is -6.1 kcal/mol, and for 7KPI is -7.53 kcal/mol [73,74]. Title compound was also docked with protein 4W93 and binding energy was found to be -4.96kcal/mol. Metformin is a clinical drug for diabetics and is docked against the protein

Human α -amylase (4W93) which has a binding energy of -4.5kcal/mol and is comparable with the chosen compound [75]. Compound under research has more negative binding energy than the standard drug. On comparing the bond parameters and the 2D docking diagram, ligand-protein interactions were found for hydrogen atom (H45), where H45 was bonded with highly electronegative oxygen (O1). A partial positive charge of H45 due to the lower electronegativity than O1, which might act as an HBD and lead to protein interaction. Other protein interactions were found for nitrogen atoms, where nitrogen atoms might be HBAs. HBD and HBA count obtained in drug-likeness are in line with the docking results. Weak hydrogen bonds were important in ligand-protein interactions and thus the biological activity of Octrizole. Results obtained from docking and other studies suggest that Octrizole might be biologically active and has strong anti-diabetic properties.

10(a)2D docking diagram of 4GQR with Octrizole.

10(b) 3D docking diagram of 4GQR with Octrizole.

10(c) 2D docking diagram of 7KPI with Octrizole.

10(d) 3D molecular docking diagram of 7KPI with Octrizole

10(e) 2D docking diagram of 4W93 with Octrizole.

10(f) 3D molecular docking diagram of 4W93 with Octrizole

Fig.10. Molecular docking diagrams of Octrizole.**Table 10** Molecular docking of Octrizole.

4	Protein (PDB ID)	Bonded residues	Bonded distance(Å°)	Binding energy (kcal/mol)	Reference RMSD(Å)
	4GQR	SER 108	2.083	-6.1	40.33
		SER 108	2		
		ARG 343	1.917		
	7KPI	GLY 132	1.907	-7.53	22.679
		UNL 1	2.772		
		UNL 1	2.861		

CONCLUSION

Density-based computational analysis with Gaussian software package and biological activity prediction on Octrizole were carried out. Optimized structure was obtained and molecular

	UNK0	2.95142		
4W93	UNK0	2.62761	-4.96	64.554
	GLN441	3.14302		
	UNK0	5.3125		
4W93(with standard drug) * [49]	ASP 197	-	-4.5	-
	GLU 233			

geometry provided insights into the structure of Octrizole. Shortest Bond length (0.972Å) was found between O1 and H45. High electronegativity of oxygen than hydrogen might be responsible for the stronger attraction of hydrogen towards oxygen and thus lead to the shortening of bond length. Vibrational analysis was employed in identifying the functional groups and thus confirmed the structure. Theoretically observed O-H peak is at 3684 cm⁻¹, which is within the range, and 100% OH stretching was found at mode 141. C-H vibration was found within the range and 100% CH stretching was observed at mode 136 with a peak of 3056 cm⁻¹. Structure determination of the chosen compound was done by analyzing the chemical shifts obtained in NMR studies. The chemical shift in ¹³C NMR spectral ranges was between 26.18ppm and 155.11ppm and ¹H NMR spectra ranged from 0.418 ppm to 8.149 ppm. Carbon atoms attached to alkyl groups or attached to heteroatom atoms (C8, C18, C19, C20) showed chemical shifts between 138 and 160 ppm which is in the desired range. Hydrogen atoms (H 47, H46, H42, H49, H48, H43, H44) are attached to aromatic rings showing chemical shifts between 7-8 ppm. Maximum absorption wavelength obtained in UV analysis was observed at 270.86 nm, a value that falls within mid-UV region of the electromagnetic spectrum indicating moderate stability and reactivity. HOMO energy was found to be -6.359 eV and LUMO was -1.749 eV and the energy gap was 4.610 eV. A softness value of 0.217 which is less than 2 indicates that the title might be low toxic. Electrophilicity index, 3.565 greater than 1.5 eV indicating the strong electrophilic nature and thus, its potential biological activity. MEP map provided the possible interactions significant in determining the biological activity of Octrizole. Positive potential near the H45 atom and negative potential near Oxygen and nitrogen atoms indicated the possible reactive sites. A hyperpolarizability value greater than urea indicated that the chosen compound was NLO active and reactive. H34 and H36 in the red area indicated a maximum probability of finding an electron, and the Nitrogen atom (N4) and carbon atoms (C8, C14, C20, C23, C24) are in the blue area suggesting the least Paul's repulsion in ELF map. LOL map also exhibits a correlation with ELF where H34 and H36 are

seen in the blue region and N4, C8, C14, C20, C23, and C24 in red region. RDG plot shows red isosurfaces near aromatic rings indicating the repulsive interaction for aromatic rings and the same results were identified in molecular geometry. Mulliken population analysis and Natural population analysis were carried out and NPA shows a very good agreement with the MEP results. Maximum positive charge was observed for the H45 atom which was bonded with an electronegative oxygen atom and negative charges were observed for oxygen and nitrogen atoms indicating that it might be an electron-rich species. Drug likeness parameters namely, LRoF, GI absorption, lipophilicity, BBB, and bioavailability score fall within the normative ranges which was comparable with the standard drug, Metformin, indicates the favourable drug character of 2-(2-Hydroxy-5-tert-octylphenyl) benzotriazole. An increased cell viability along with the decreased concentration was found in in vitro assay studies. Stability of 4GQR and 7KPI, 4W93 was indicated by their RC plots since a large number of amino acid residues are located inside the permitted zone and these proteins are suitable in molecular docking. Binding energy of title compound and standard drug metformin with protein 4W93 is -4.96kcal/mol and -4.5kcal/mol respectively. Binding energy of chosen compound was found to be more negative than standard drug suggesting that octrizole might be a potent compound. Biological evaluation of Octrizole predicts that it might be an agent in treating diabetics.

Disclosure of Interest

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

Author Contribution Statement

DONA BENNY: Validation, Visualization, Data curation, Writing- original draft

A. Anuradha: Writing- review and editing

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